

Panel Flutter Analysis of Composite Plates with Structural Damping Using Finite Elements

Kyo-Nam Koo

*Division of Aerospace Eng., School of Transportation Systems Engineering, University of Ulsan
Ulsan 680-74, South Korea*

And

Dong-Hyun Kim

*School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering and ReCAPT, Gyeongsang National University
Jinju, Gyeongnam 660-702, South Korea*

ABSTRACT

A research on the effect of structural damping on the panel flutter of composite plates, to author's knowledge, has not been reported whereas many papers have investigated the effect on the panel flutter of isotropic plates. Governing equation for the finite element analysis of panel flutter of composite plates including structural damping is derived using Hamilton's principle. The first-order shear deformable plate theory is applied to structural modeling so as to obtain the finite element eigenvalue equation. The unsteady aerodynamic load in a supersonic flow is computed by the linear piston theory. The critical dynamic pressures for composite plate are calculated to investigate the effect of structural damping on flutter boundaries.

KEYWORDS: structural damping, panel flutter, composite plates.

INTRODUCTION

Panel flutter is a dynamic instability of thin skin of flight vehicles occurring at a critical velocity of the airflow passing on it. Jordan [1] is known as the first person who was aware of panel flutter on flight structures and suggested that a lot of early V-2 rocket failures might result from panel flutter. Many researches [2-8] on the panel flutter of isotropic plates have been carried out since 1950's. A lot of papers [9-11] attempted the panel flutter analysis of composite plates after the composite materials were broadly used in the aerospace structures in 1980's.

A research on the effect of structural damping on the panel flutter of composite plates, to author's knowledge, has not been reported whereas many papers have investigated the effect on the panel flutter of isotropic plates. In general, damping in structures is a favorable property in aspect of passively controlling the dynamic responses. However, the uniformly distributed damping due to the structural deformation may reduce the stability of panel flutter. Ellen [5] illustrated that the hysteretic damping and the viscous damping can destabilize the system by making the effect of aerodynamic damping decreased. Lottati [13] showed that viscous damping reduces the stability of isotropic beam. Though Oyibo [14] analyzed the panel flutter of composite plates, the damping of composite plate was modeled as a dashpot in neglect of the uniformly distributed damping due to bending deformation. It can be said that his result could not reflect the correct damping mechanism of composite plates and the effect of fiber orientation.

In this paper, the finite element method formulates the equation of motion for damped panel flutter of composite plate using the first-order shear deformable plate theory. High Mach number approximation to the linear potential flow theory, i.e., the linear piston theory that is suitable for $M > \sqrt{2}$ is utilized to compute the unsteady aerodynamic load on the panel. This paper adopts the

hysteretic damping model since it is more realistic than the viscous damping model in structural vibration. The effect of structural damping on the flutter boundaries of composite plates is investigated with the change of fiber orientation and the amount of aerodynamic damping.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

The displacement field in the first-order shear deformable plate theory can be expressed of the form:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} u_0 \\ v_0 \\ w_0 \end{Bmatrix} - z \begin{Bmatrix} \phi_x \\ \phi_y \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where u , v , and w are the displacement components in the x , y , z directions, respectively; ϕ_x and ϕ_y are the rotations about y and x axes, respectively; and the subscript 0 denotes the mid-plane.

Hamilton's principle formulates the finite element equation of damped panel flutter as follows:

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \delta(T - U + W_{nc}) dt = 0 \quad (2)$$

where T is the kinetic energy; U is the potential energy; W_{nc} is the work done by non-conservative forces; and δ is a variational operator.

The kinetic energy for symmetric laminated plate can be obtained:

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \delta T dt = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_V \rho \dot{\mathbf{u}}^T \delta \dot{\mathbf{u}} dV dt = -\hat{m} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_0^a \int_0^b (I \ddot{\phi}_x \delta \phi_x + I \ddot{\phi}_y \delta \phi_y + \ddot{w} \delta w) dx dy dt \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the density of plate, $\mathbf{u}^T = \{u \quad v \quad w\}$, $\hat{m} = \rho h$ and $I = (\int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \rho z^2 dz) / \rho h$.

The bending strain energy for symmetric laminated plate is given by:

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \delta U dt = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_V \boldsymbol{\sigma}^T \delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon} dV dt = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_0^a \int_0^b \boldsymbol{\chi}^T \mathbf{D} \delta \boldsymbol{\chi} dx dy dt \quad (4)$$

Here $\boldsymbol{\chi}^T = \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial \phi_x}{\partial x} \right) \quad \left(\frac{\partial \phi_y}{\partial y} \right) \quad \left(\frac{\partial \phi_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \phi_y}{\partial x} \right) \quad \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} + \phi_y \right) \quad \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} + \phi_x \right) \right\}$ and \mathbf{D} is the bending stiffness of laminated plate and defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} D_{ij} &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k z^2 dz \quad \text{for } i, j = 1, 2, 3 \\ D_{ij} &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k dz \quad \text{for } i, j = 4, 5 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{Q}}_k = \mathbf{R}_k^{-1} \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{R}_k^{-T}$ is the transformed reduced stiffness of the k -th layer; \mathbf{R}_k is the transformation matrix; \mathbf{Q} is the reduced stiffness matrix of an orthotropic lamina; and its definition can be found in Reference 14.

The virtual work by non-conservative force δW_{nc} is composed of the virtual work by aerodynamic force, δW_A and the virtual work by structural damping, δW_D .

$$\delta W_{nc} = \delta W_A + \delta W_D \quad (6)$$

Using a first-order high Mach number approximation to the linear potential flow theory, which is suitable for $M > \sqrt{2}$, δW_A becomes

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \delta W_A dt = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_0^a \int_0^b q \delta w dx dy dt = - \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_0^a \int_0^b \left(\beta \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} + \mu \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \right) \delta w dx dy dt \quad (7)$$

where $\beta = \rho_a V^2 / \sqrt{M^2 - 1}$, $\mu = \rho_a V (M^2 - 2) / (M^2 - 1)^{1.5}$; ρ_a , V , and M are the density, velocity, and Mach number of free stream, respectively.

Assuming the structural damping to be hysteretic can make δW_D expressed by

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \delta W_D dt = - \frac{1}{\omega} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_V \dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^T \bar{\mathbf{H}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} dV dt = - \frac{1}{\omega} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_0^a \int_0^b \dot{\boldsymbol{\chi}}^T \mathbf{G} \boldsymbol{\chi} dx dy dt \quad (8)$$

Here $\bar{\mathbf{H}}$ is a diagonal matrix with non-zero components $\bar{h}_{11} = \eta_x$, $\bar{h}_{22} = \eta_y$, $\bar{h}_{33} = \eta_{xy}$, $\bar{h}_{44} = \eta_{yz}$, $\bar{h}_{55} = \eta_{xz}$ and \mathbf{G} is the damping matrix due to bending and defined as:

$$G_{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \bar{Q}_{ij}^H z^2 dz \quad \text{for } i, j = 1, 2, 3 \quad \text{and} \quad G_{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \bar{Q}_{ij}^H dz \quad \text{for } i, j = 4, 5 \quad (9)$$

where $\bar{Q}_k^H = \mathbf{R}_k^{-1} \mathbf{H} \mathbf{Q}_k^{-T}$ and \mathbf{H} is a diagonal matrix with non-zero components $h_{11} = \eta_1$, $h_{22} = \eta_2$, $h_{33} = \eta_{12}$, $h_{44} = \eta_{23}$, $h_{55} = \eta_{13}$. η_1 and η_2 denote the loss factors in 0 deg. and 90 deg. directions of a lamina, and η_{12} , η_{23} , and η_{13} are the loss factors by shear.

Substitution of the expressions in Equations (3), (4), (7), and (8) into Equation (2) derives a variational formulation of the problem. The finite element method interpolates the displacements in a linear combination of shape functions like:

$$(w, \phi_x, \phi_y) = \sum_{i=1}^n (\bar{w}_i, \bar{\phi}_{xi}, \bar{\phi}_{yi}) N_i(x, y) \quad (10)$$

where $N_i(x, y)$ is the Lagrange family of interpolation functions and n is the number of nodes per element.

The finite element equation can be written substituting Equation (10) into the variational formulation:

$$\hat{m} \mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{u}} + \left(\frac{1}{\omega} \mathbf{C} + \mu \mathbf{M} \right) \dot{\mathbf{u}} + (\beta \mathbf{A} + \mathbf{K}) \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0} \quad (11)$$

Assuming the vibration to be stationary, i.e., $\mathbf{u}(t) = \bar{\mathbf{u}} e^{i\omega t}$, transforms the flutter equation into the eigenvalue equation:

$$[(i\mathbf{C} + \mathbf{K} + \beta \mathbf{A}) - \lambda \mathbf{M}] \bar{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{0} \quad (12)$$

where an eigenvalue is defined as $\lambda = \omega^2 \hat{m} - i\omega\mu$.

In the case for $\beta = 0$, composite plate undergoes a damped free vibration with \mathbf{C} and an undamped

free vibration without \mathbf{C} . If the aerodynamic damping μ is considered, it is the critical dynamic pressure β_{cr} at which the computed aerodynamic damping $\mu = \lambda_i / \sqrt{\lambda_R / \hat{m}}$ coincides with the aerodynamic damping assumed according to the flight condition.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

The nine-noded 6×6 elements are employed and only the clamped square plate with the length-to-thickness ratio of $a/h = b/h = 200$ is considered in this paper. Figure 1 shows the geometric definition of composite plate in supersonic airflow.

The composite material used in this analysis is HMS/DX-210 of which properties are given as [15]:

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 = 172.7 \text{ GPa}, E_2 = 7.2 \text{ GPa}, G_{12} = 3.76 \text{ GPa}, \nu_{12} = 0.3, \rho = 1550 \text{ Kg/m}^3 \\ \eta_1 = 7.162 \times 10^{-4}, \eta_2 = 6.716 \times 10^{-3}, \eta_{12} = \eta_{23} = \eta_{13} = 1.122 \times 10^{-2} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Figure 1. Geometric definition of composite plate in airflow.

Figure 2. (a) Real eigenvalue λ_R^* and (b) Imaginary eigenvalue λ_I^* of $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ clamped square plate. — $\eta_{ij} = 0$; - - - η_{ij} ; - · - · $10 \times \eta_{ij}$; ρ , \square , \leq flutter points.

1. QUASI-ISOTROPIC COMPOSITE PLATE

Figure 2 shows the non-dimensional real eigenvalue $\lambda_R^* = \lambda_R a^4 / E_2 h^3$ and imaginary one $\lambda_I^* = \lambda_I a^4 / E_2 h^3$ of the critical modes vs. the non-dimensional dynamic pressure $\beta^* = \beta a^3 / E_2 h^3$ for a quasi-isotropic composite plate $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$. The solid line (—) means the eigenvalues when the structural damping η_{ij} is neglected, i.e., $\eta_{ij} = 0$; the dashed line (-----) denotes the eigenvalues when the structural damping η_{ij} given in Equation (13) is included; the centered line (-.-.-) is obtained by increasing the structural damping η_{ij} in Equation (13) by ten times, i.e., $10 \times \eta_{ij}$. In the case for $\eta_{ij} = 0$, two real eigenvalues λ_R^* approach to each other with increasing β^* and then merge into a pair of complex conjugate after the flutter occurs. This phenomenon is called frequency coalescence. In the case for $\eta_{ij} \neq 0$, the eigenvalues λ^* are complex for any value of β^* except for zero. The real parts of two eigenvalues, λ_R^* approach to each other but do not coalesce. In this case, flutter occurs when an imaginary part of an eigenvalue λ_I^* changes from positive to negative. It is seen that the critical dynamic pressure in the case for $\eta_{ij} \neq 0$ is greatly reduced as compared to that for $\eta_{ij} = 0$. It is observed in Figure 2 that the critical flutter occurs with relation to modes 9 and 10 for both $\eta_{ij} = 0$ and η_{ij} , but to mode 1 and 2 for $10 \times \eta_{ij}$. It is noted that the flutter with relation to modes 9 and 10, which will be designated the flutter of mode 9/10 hereafter, is a weak flutter instability which becomes stable with increment of structural damping. The natural mode shapes and flutter mode shapes are illustrated in Figure 3. It is shown that the flutter mode shapes look like a combination of two related natural modes.

Figure 3. Natural mode shapes and flutter mode shape of $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ clamped square plate.

Figure 4. Critical dynamic pressure for $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ with variation of structural damping

Figure 5. Critical dynamic pressure for $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ with variation of aerodynamic damping

Figure 4 illustrates the critical dynamic pressures β_{cr}^* vs. the magnification factor n of the material loss factors η_{ij} for several values of μ . It is interesting that the instability occurs in the flutter of mode 9/10 when the structural damping is small but in the flutter of mode 1/2 when the structural damping is large. Also, it is worthwhile noting that the structural damping may stabilize or destabilize the flutter instability depending on the type of flutter. The flutter of mode 1/2 is destabilized with increase of the structural damping and the flutter of mode 9/10 which is a weak flutter is stabilized with increase of the structural damping.

The lowest β_{cr}^* vs. μ for various structural damping shown in Figure 5 indicates that the effect of aerodynamic damping on the stability for the flutter of mode 9/10 is different from that for the flutter of mode 1/2. The flutter of mode 9/10 shows a nearly constant stability at the large values of aerodynamic damping whereas the flutter of mode 1/2 shows the high increasing rate of stability at the low values of aerodynamic damping.

2. ORTHOTROPIC COMPOSITE PLATE

Figure 6 shows the effect of the structural damping on the critical dynamic pressure of $[\theta]_S$ plate with variation of fiber orientation θ for three values of aerodynamic damping, $\mu = 0, 10, 100$. The lines in Figure 6 denote the critical dynamic pressures of the flutter of mode 1/2 except for $\theta = 0$ deg. where the instability occurs in the flutter of mode 1/6. The symbols circle (\square) and triangle (ρ) mean the critical pressures of flutter modes other than mode 1/2. The critical dynamic pressure decreases as the fiber orientation increases because the bending stiffness in the flow direction, D_{11} decreases with increasing fiber orientation. The critical dynamic pressures of the flutter of mode 1/2 with the structural damping (designated as ———) are much smaller than those without the structural damping (designated as - - - - -) and the trends of those two cases are similar to each other. The critical dynamic pressures with the structural damping approach to those without the structural damping for $\mu = 0$ as the aerodynamic damping μ increases. This is because the aerodynamic damping becomes much bigger compared to the structural damping. The flutter instability occurs in different modes at some fiber orientations. For example, the instability occurs in the flutter of mode 8/9 at $\theta = 50$ deg., which is weak flutter and the structural damping stabilizes the flutter.

The amount of decrement in β_{cr}^* by the structural damping in flutter analysis for $\mu = 0, 10, 100$ is shown in Figure 7 with variation of fiber orientation. The instability in Figure 7 is the flutter of mode 1/2 besides $\theta = 0$ deg. as is in Figure 6. $\bar{\beta}_{cr}^*$ denotes the critical dynamic pressures normalized by the

Figure 6. Critical dynamic pressure vs. fiber orientation θ .

Figure 7. Ratio of β_{cr}^* with structural damping to β_{cr}^* with no structural damping

dynamic pressure at $\theta = 0$ deg. when $\eta_{ij} = 0$ and $\mu = 0$. It is observed that the reduction of β_{cr}^* by the structural damping is largest near $\theta = 45$ deg.

The modal loss factors of the natural modes 1, 2 and flutter mode are shown in Figure 8 so as to understand the relationship between $\bar{\beta}_{cr}^*$ and θ . The modal loss factors of the modes 1 and 2 are relatively large near $\theta = 45$ deg. The modal loss factor of the flutter mode has a value between those of the modes 1 and 2. This illustrates that the decrement in β_{cr}^* by the structural damping is large when the modal loss factors related to flutter mode is large.

CONCLUSIONS

The finite element method is applied to study the effect of distributed structural damping on the flutter boundaries of composite plates.

(1) Structural damping may stabilize or destabilize the flutter instability of composite plate depending on the type of flutter. This means that the effect of structural damping is dependent on the fiber orientation of composite plate because the flutter mode can be weak or strong according to the fiber orientation.

(2) The effect of structural damping on the panel flutter of composite plate is important as aerodynamic damping decreases, i.e., altitude increases.

(3) The fiber orientation of composite plate has little influence on the reduction of the critical dynamic pressure due to structural damping when aerodynamic damping is high.

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Figure 8. Modal loss factors vs. fiber orientation θ of first, second natural modes and flutter modes.

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